

Thomistic Theory of Personal Relations

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0. Introduction

Formulation of the theory of personal relations- including the very phrase “personal relations”- is the unquestioned legacy of Mieczysław Gogacz, the founder of Consistent Thomism. This theory is a typical example of philosophical consequences drawn from the views of Aquinas, even though Thomas himself employs the term “personal relation” occasionally only, and nowhere further he provides its wider explanation. The topic of relations in general, especially personal relations, became the subject of deeper studies by stu-

dents of Gogacz. It is them who – even when vividly questioning some ideas of their teacher - continue the fundamental insights of the founder of Consistent Thomism. Therefore, for the purpose of this presentation, we are limited here to the introduction of the theory of personal relations by the Professor.

Gogacz himself claimed that an inspiration for the theory of personal relations derives from Martin Buber’s work (*Ja i Ty*). When studying the first formula of the above theory (in a book: *Wokół problemu osoby*) one cannot escape

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the impression that the foundation of the theory of personal relations can be found to some extent, in the views of Mieczysław Krąpiec on the relative character of some transcendentals which serve the fundament for the real unity of the world. The final formula of Gogacz's theory of personal relations is found in his *Elementarz metafizyki* and in the book published two years prior to it, titled *Człowiek i jego relacje*. In further publications, there are following proposals for implementing the theory of personal relations in practice such as ethics (*Wprowadzenie do etyki chronienia osób*), pedagogy (*Osoba celem pedagogiki*) and even politics (*Mądrość buduje państwo*). Much earlier, on the basis of the aforementioned theory, the Professor built his theological approaches (*Filozoficzne aspekty mistyki, Modlitwa i mistyka*).

Further steps in the development of the theory of personal relations are remarks and commentaries developed by Gogacz's students who continue his thought. Many of them attempted to apply this theory in many more specific or even practical domains: Jakub Wójcik in pedagogy of family, Krzysztof Woj-

ciech in prevention, Artur Andrzejuk in ethics, Krzysztof Kalka in school pedagogy. Some of them – such as Wójcik and Andrzejuk – added their own thought to Gogacz's formulas. Ryszard Kalka and Władysław Kubiak developed metaphysical aspects of the theory and expressed numerous varied doubts.

Professor Gogacz, like everyone else who addressed questions on a topic of personal relations, worked on the source texts of Thomas Aquinas. Although it is omitted in this paper, it is necessary to remind that the greatest autonomous text regarding this topic is *Questiones disputate de caritate*. Their main concern is love between man and God. In *Summa Theologiae*, there is – rather short and scattered in its various parts – an overall conception of love, faith and hope. Hence, God's love is shown by Thomas in the question *De amore Dei* (I,20), theory of feelings is included in *Treatise on emotions* (I-II,22-48), and finally there is *Treatise on love* (II-II, 23-44) which principally explores rational love – *dilectio*, while separate treatises are dedicated to faith (II-II, 1-6) and hope (II-II,17-22).

I. Theory of personal relations and philosophical topics inferred by Mieczysław Gogacz

In a particular being, personal relations are built in the manifestation of its existence and are the most primary, the most initial, the most natural interper-

sonal reference, such as the most primary and initial is existence in beings. There are three personal relations: love, faith and hope.

1.1. Personal relations of love

Love – as Gogacz says – builds upon the existential property of reality and is, like

reality, primary and a datum point with regard to other existential relations. It

is a “benevolent coexistence of persons” (*Elementarz*, 103). Love is described in terms of the results it causes in persons. Hence, we speak of an encounter in the fact of their reality: mutual affinity, mutual benevolence, acceptance, mutual appropriateness, and openness.

M. Gogacz enumerates – following St. Thomas – various kinds of love.

1) *Connaturalitas (complacentia)*.

Its nature is complacency (*complacentia*), which brings about acceptance, and hence, an attitude of kindness. This kind of love is brought about by the characteristics present in two beings, which is the adequacy of existence and the fact that both of them are persons. This relation is of connatural character (*connaturalitas*).

2) *Concupiscibilitas (concupiscentia)*.

This kind of love in a specific mode, also through emotions, encompasses the body of man. Its deep motive is beauty which exactly causes delight, adoration, tenderness (affection), sometimes jealousy, and even anger. Although this kind of love is richer by sensual good, it still this good considered only as good for us (*quo ad nos*), what we call desire (*concupiscentia*).

3) *Dilectio*

Dilectio is full personal love. In this love, we encompass, through intellect, the entire person, along with his understandings and deci-

sions. In the act of willing goodness, we will that what the beloved person wills. Personal love has several levels.

a) Friendship (*amicitia*) is full gratitude, faithfulness (that is persistence of love) and full trust. It does not cause anxiety or fear. It is expressed by complete mutuality.

b) Love which does not expect mutuality (*caritas*). Its shape is selflessness, full care, and protection of our own well-being. It has a forgiving, discrete, sacrificial character. This love occurs as the theme of St. Paul’s Hymn of Love (1 Kor 13), says Gogacz.

c) Love related to sorrow (*amor*) is grounded in constant longing for the presence of the beloved person. Absence causes longing accompanied by sorrow. In this, we find a typical human love. And this love is a simple love of man to God. Gogacz is convinced that this kind of love is described in Song of Songs.

d) Love of God to man (*agape*) is characterized – according to Christian Revelation – by absolute selflessness. It is a specific union of friendship and *caritas*. The Psalms show more intelligible explanation of this love.

1.2. Personal relations of faith and hope

Faith is a relation which builds upon the property of truth. Thus, it is a mutual

openness of persons and trust. It cannot be identified with cognition and knowl-

edge. In the subjective approach, that is with regard to ourselves, faith is a confident and open attitude toward the other person. In the objective sense, it is an openness to everything that the other person brings into this relation.

In the relation of faith, concerning God, faith is a supernatural, proper to God, mode of giving Himself to ourselves. In the subjective sense, it is confidence in God, His veracity, is what concerns God himself. Hence, in this

aspect, the acceptance of the revealed truth is included (Cf. *Rola wiary w życiu chrześcijanina*).

Hope is subjected in person by goodness as the manifestation of his existence. Thus, hope is everything that brings about goodness. It arises from the expectation that a person, an object of our faith and love, will reciprocate and protect the relation (*Elementarz*, 108, *Człowiek*, 15).

1.3. Issues of humanism and religion

Personal relations are the most fundamental mutual references of persons. According to the favourite Gogacz's phrase, personal relations are simply a home for the person (Cf. *Kościół moim domem*). This home, when built on references of man with human beings, is humanism. When love, faith and hope relate man with the Divine Persons – we speak of religion.

Humanism and religion, as the fundamental environment of human being, demands care and protection. The primary aim is that man should recog-

nize them as precious. There is a need for education of people on humanism and religion for a proper understanding of human being, the world and God. As for man, to be able to protect the perseverance of personal relations, it is crucial to obtain knowledge on how to proceed. Diverse skills and abilities are then important. The upbringing to humanism and religion is also crucial. It guarantees the process of persistence of man in these references, persistence among persons, deprived of which man dies and perishes.

1.4. Persistence of personal relations as value

Mieczysław Gogacz introduces a new description of value related to the theory of personal relations and formulated on the ground of classical metaphysics: "*quod intellectum et approbatum continuatur*" (*Człowiek*, 88).

Recognition of personal relations and the decision to let them persist as end and goal of man related by them with other persons indicates the essential human values: persistence of fundamental per-

sonal relations. Hence, there is a definition: value is the persistence of a result caused in a human being by fundamental relations that connect him with other persons. It occurs when man, on the basis of his understanding and decision, seeks persistence of these relations as the end and goal.

In defining a value as the persistence of the relation of benevolence, openness and trust between persons, we exclude

understanding a value as a value of anything. Thus, we eliminate any random, axiological or even openly ideological basis for defining a value. Let us notice that a value, as such defined, cannot be identified with any (speaking of the language of the philosophy of Aristotle) substance or property. Therefore,

a value is not a man. Personal relations are not values either, not even the greatest among them- love. Value is the process of persistence in love and, what is more, not in love of whatever its object appears, but only of love linking persons with themselves.

2. Remarks and suggestions of Mieczysław Gogacz followers

2.1. Structure of personal relations

According to Gogacz, there are two layers distinguished in the structure of personal relations: the existential and essential (*Tomizm...*, 103). The former layer is indicated by the manifestation of the act of existence, which arises when a relation between two persons takes place. The latter stratum is what these relations contribute to the essence of persons. Kubiak asks whether we may speak of one relation only or two and posits a question on the possibility of change of relation in its essential layer (*Ogólna charakterystyka...*, 64-64).

In his works, Thomas Aquinas left only a general description of the structure of relations. Thus, we need to turn to this description in order to study the structure of personal relations. It seems that Kubiak is right when he says that when there is an absence of an identical order in whichever of its ends, it results in the lack of personal relation. An

example of this kind of relations would be hence: "relation of person" and relations "regarding a person" (*Teoria...*, 90). The former takes place when the subject of relations is a person, and its end is an impersonal being. This type of relation lacks the personal element on the part of existence. We may classify relations of impersonal subject and personal end within the latter type.

There are, however, relations in which subject and end are placed in the same order when both their subject and end are personal beings. Nevertheless, their relation cannot be classified within the frame of personal relations. According to Kubiak, what is decisive for concluding whether a relation is personal and what distinguishes personal relations from other ones is, apart from the subject and end, which are in the same order, the personal character of the essence of the relation.

2.2. Faith as personal relation

When analysing the personal relations of faith and hope, we need to mention the profound meaning of one more

characteristic of these relations, which is that they are responsive (symmetrical or twofold). This statement regards the

classical definition of relation understood as *ordo unius ad aliud*, where one substance is a subject of relation and the other is its end. Active behaviour of the subject of the relation is called *actio*; passive behaviour of its end – *passio*. Each person involved in a personal relation is both its subject and its end; therefore, each person involved experiences both *action* and *passio*. This standpoint allows to analyse deeper the essential stratum of these two personal relations.

The existential property of truth indicates faith as a personal relation. As a return relation, faith is thus a spe-

cific mutual exchange of truth and also its mutual transferring. Hence, the process of transferring truth to someone, an active behaviour in the act of its exchange, is referred to as truthfulness. Truthfulness hence, is the essence of the personal relation of faith considered in its active aspect. Trust is the *conditio* for accepting the truth transferred by someone to us. Trust, hence, is the essence of the personal relations of faith in its passive aspect. Therefore, we may say that truthfulness and trust are the essence or nature of personal relations of hope (*Prawda o dobru*, 247-248).

2.2.1. Union of the personal relation of faith with the categorial relation of cognition

When a relation is grounded in the properties of truth of both involved persons – they are connected with the personal relation of faith. When a relation indicated by the property of truth of some being finds its end in someone else's cognitive powers, for example, in the possible intellect of a human person, we deal with the categorial cognitive relation. It seems, therefore, that the entire relation of cognition in some way belongs to the area of the existential relation of faith. It has a particular meaning in teaching and any process of transferring knowledge; hence, it is rooted in the area and atmosphere of the personal relation of faith.

We can imagine what impediments may a lie, as the opposition of trustfulness, bring about into functioning personal relations. It undermines trust and extinguishes the personal relation of faith. In love of *dilectio*, it makes the friendship- the most partnership shape

of this personal relation- impossible to initiate. Similarly, negative effects are brought about by a lie in love on the affective level. Since emotions are references to imaginations, when they are built on a lie, it means that our feelings are built on false imaginations, such as those regarding the other person. Life, sooner or later, will verify the false imaginations; however, it might be too late from the perspective of results already caused.

Lack of trust inhibits the process of development of personal union, extinguishes partnership, takes advantage of someone's sincerity, and thus puts a strain on the personal relation of faith. Nevertheless, we need to stress that always active is prior to what is passive. Hence, it is truthfulness that makes us deserving of someone's trust, not otherwise: trust rarely makes someone truthful. Moreover, it is much more difficult to regain trust once a priori given (at a

specific credit). All these observations prove the aforementioned dependen-

cy of trust on truthfulness (*Prawda o dobru*, 249-250).

2.3. Hope as personal relation

The personal relation of hope is indicated through the existential property of goodness. It is hence a specific exchange of some good in its essential layer. In its active aspect, the foundation of this exchange is showing goodness, doing goodness (*benefacientia*) as an attitude of wishing goodness for others, which we may refer to as benevolence (*benevolentia*). In its passive aspect, the hope is openness to the goodness brought about by the other person. At the same time, it is a sort of ability to accept a gift. This mutual exchange of good is – as claims Aristotle – the essence of friendship.

According to Gogacz, in a personal relation of hope, our behaviour is included as a relation toward goodness. The behaviour, however, is not solely a categorial relation as, it is rather a personal relation, because I truly attain to the good I hope for. Hence, the conduct – as Gogacz used to say – transfers us from the encounter (categorial relations) to the presence (personal relations), “mainly into the relation of hope, as this relation is subjected in two beings by transcendental property of goodness” (*Elementarz metafizyki*, 91).

2.3.1. The union of hope with the relation of conduct

Mieczysław Gogacz in *Elementarz metafizyki* (91-92) observes that the relation of conduct while belonging to the set of categorial relations is subjected to the will. Its end is a being in its aspect of goodness. Thus, the relation is subjected to the will and “attains” only this aspect of being. It does not encompass a being directly, as the will cannot leave the existential area of man whose power it is itself. This existential area can be trespassed by personal relations only, as they are built on the manifestations *esse* of being, and it is inherited in their nature to trespass a categorial content of being. That is why M. Gogacz thinks that the will stimulates transcendental properties for subjecting personal relations. In light of the above, we may assume that the relation of conduct is

a specific “passage” from encounter to presence.

When we want to indicate the “nature” of this “passage”, we should focus on the relevance of the personal relation of hope with the categorial relation of conduct on the basis that for both of them, the existential property of good is their end. Thus, we may claim that conduct specifically belongs to a domain or range of the personal relation of hope.

Mieczysław Gogacz also observes a particular union of both domains, hope and ethics. Moral philosophy, when built on such ground, is also close to the philosophy of St. Thomas, who clearly links hope with goodness and happiness as the result of the possession of goodness (S.Th. II-II, 17, 2c).

3. Summary: Presence as the result of duration of personal relations

Presence is one of the earliest philosophical and theological topics (*Wprowadzenie do etyki chronienia osób*, 15-29; *Teoria relacji...*, 65-71). There is a reasonable suspicion that some philosophical traditions (for example, Neoplatonism) are simply theories of presence. “En-

counter” as a philosophical problem arose relatively recently and has been popularized through the fashionable philosophy of the subject. In this situation, we may attempt to interpret both encounter and presence in the context of the theory of personal relations.

3.1. Differentiation between encounter and presence

On the one hand, we are entitled to make such a differentiation on the basis of the texts of St. Thomas, who employs the term *praesentia* exactly to express the fact of remaining persons in relations through love (*Super Sententias* III, d. 22, q. 3, 1; S. Th I, 8, 3, ad 4). On the other hand, this differentiation has been specifically provoked by the topic of “encounter” present in contemporary philosophy, especially the philosophy of the subject.

This differentiation is already visible in the etymological meaning of the words “encounter” and “presence”. Therefore, an encounter is associated with meeting people temporarily, while presence is something more durable. An encounter would be a moment of infatuation between two persons at the beginning of their relationship. Their further stable relation in the shape of marriage will not be denoted an encounter, as it will be the presence of two persons on a daily basis in their lives. On that ground, we may speak of an encounter as of any meeting of persons with regard to functions they fulfil: teacher-pupil, clerk-suppliant, doctor-patient. As we

meet each other, however, we are always in some relative system; usually, these are intellectual relations, in which the other person is present as someone who delivers some sort of good to us; occasionally, this desired good is directly something that belongs to the personal or essential property of the person, for example, their knowledge, grace, sense of humour. When described in the aforementioned terms, the encounters can be characterized by two primary features:

- assignment of function is the feature of a thing (a product)
- encounter is “objectification” of a person

Presence is an encounter of persons on the basis that they are persons. Thus, personal relations are the shape of presence. Hence, only within a frame of presence can we initiate relations with the other person on the ground that they are a person. What we deal here with is not the reduction of person to the role of a product or “tool” to achieve our goals. In light of the above, we may formulate a postulate for initiating intellectual relations with regard to per-

sons only in the area of presence. Then, within the intellectual relations, the re-

duction of person solely to the functions he fulfils would not take place.

3.2. Personal relations of presence

Considering presence as the process of functioning of relations of love, faith and hope in communities of person, we may say that these three relations are the shape of presence and that the essence of this presence is the personal relation of love. Further, the personal relations of faith and hope are the mode for protection of this presence and, particularly in it, the personal relation of love. Thus, this protection is possible through the activity of the intellect and the will, that is, in knowledge and conduct. Hence, the personal relation of faith “activates” cognitive activities protecting love; similarly personal relations of hope encourage an activity for protecting persons and their mutual correlations.

Also, we may treat divisions known from literature as kinds of love. In the Thomistic categories presented above, we may clearly notice the differences between particular levels and sorts of love. Primarily, friendship – a kind of love cherished by Aristotle and Thomas the most – seems to be a full and harmonious functioning of all three personal relations. Only such circumstances can bring fruit in what Aristotle and

Thomas stressed in their description of friendship: full mutuality, full trust, constant readiness to offer help. In “caritas”, understood as a shape of presence, the personal relation of hope seems to dominate. In *caritas*, there is an aspect of longing for good recognised in the presence of a beloved person. Christian moralists were right when they thought of God as the Highest human Good and the ultimate goal for human life. Compassion (mercy) means a dominance of faith as trust and truthfulness. Truth discovered in relation of cognition expresses the needs and deficiencies- remedies to which compassion attempts to find. Domination of personal relation of faith in compassion causes specific indifference toward one’s own goodness, genuine altruism, and not expecting anything for oneself.

The theory of personal relations can, therefore, be regarded as a Thomistic version of a topic of presence, accomplished by religion understood as personal relations of a human being with God, and by humanism considered as interpersonal references.

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